

To whom it may concern

Aug 29, 2024

EVALUATION LETTER

Regarding:

Student: MOHAMMAD RAZA IBRAHIM

Group: Tour-123M

Master Thesis Topic: The Impact of The Great Silk Road on Current Tourism

Hereby I confirm that the thesis mentioned here accomplished by the student and ready for the upcoming defense procedure according to all necessary rules, procedures, and timeline.

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Dr. Khusen Ibragimov', enclosed in a faint rectangular box.

Dr. Khusen Ibragimov

Tourism Management Department